

Analysis of heat stress in classrooms of different school building types

Type of school building of the Post-war period:

Altbauteil des Ehrenfried-Walther-von-Tschirnhaus-Gymnasiums in Dresden

Authors:

Subhashree Nath, Dr. Christoph Schünemann

Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development e.V., Dresden

Published on 18.09.2025

Approach and goals

Climate change is leading to higher temperatures and more frequent heat waves, which is particularly dangerous for children under the age of 12. School classes are often in classrooms for more than six hours a day, which affects health, well-being and learning performance at high room temperatures. Since pupils can hardly influence the temperatures, they are particularly at risk. In addition, the school building stock is usually not designed for increasingly hot summers and tends to overheat anyway due to the large window areas of classrooms. The joint project KlimaKonform II therefore investigated how high the heat load is in classrooms of different school building types in Saxony, Saxony-Anhalt and Thuringia and which heat adaptation measures are particularly effective.

This study uses a combined approach to analyse heat stress and thermal comfort in seven schools. These include three schools from the Gründerzeit period (1870–1918) in Plauen, Dresden and Gera, two prefabricated schools (1970–1990) in Zeitz and Dresden, a school from the post-war period (1952) in Dresden and a newly built school, also in Dresden. The comparison can be used to determine which building types are particularly susceptible to extreme heat stress.

This profile reports on the results on heat stress and thermal comfort in the post-war school building type, based on the old building part of the Ehrenfried-Walther-von-Tschirnhaus-Gymnasium in Dresden.

The analysis follows the process shown in the diagram below and consists of several steps:

- **Step a: Selection of representative school buildings**
- **Step B: Temperature measurements in classrooms**
Continuous measurement of classroom and outdoor temperatures from June to the end of September 2024 in two classrooms per school.
- **Step C: Survey of pupils and teachers on the perceived heat stress**
At the same time, pupils and their teachers in the two classrooms per school were asked how they felt about the indoor climate in summer. The survey makes it possible to record temperature-dependent well-being.
- **Step D: Effectiveness analysis of heat adaptation via thermal building simulation**
In addition, detailed 3D models of the examined classrooms were created for thermal building simulations. In this way, the effectiveness of different adaptation measures can be tested and compared in simulations.

Linking these steps (a to d) ensures that both objectively measured and subjectively perceived aspects of thermal comfort are taken into account.

This profile focuses mainly on structural-technical and behavioural adaptation to reduce heat stress in classrooms. The equally relevant school organisational measures (location of the summer holiday period, shortened lessons, switching to cooler classrooms) and schoolyard design aspects are not the subject of this profile.

Ehrenfried-Walther-von-Tschirnhaus-Gymnasium in Dresden

a General information about the school

Description

The "Ehrenfried-Walther-von-Tschirnhaus-Gymnasium" is located in the city of Dresden (Saxony). The school consists of two building sections. The older part examined here is a typical example of a school building of the post-war period with solid brick walls and reinforced concrete ceilings. In 2019, the old building was extensively renovated and the large windows were modernized with thermal insulation glazing. The classrooms do not have external sun protection, but only internal glare protection. The classrooms examined are oriented to the southeast and northeast.

Source: Google Earth, 07/2022

Sources: Christoph Schünemann, 06/2024

General information

School level	Gymnasium
Construction type	Post-war period (Year of construction 1952)
Address	Bernhardstraße 18 01069 Dresden
Status of the renovation	Completely renovated in 2019 (façade uninsulated)
Grade levels taken into account	7th and 8th grade

Klassenzimmer Südostfassade (Room A161)

Floor space	76,8 m²
Orientation of the windows	South-East
Window glazing	Thermal insulation glazing (built in 2018) (Total energy transmittance glazing 52 %)
Shading	Only internal glare protection (no external sun protection)
Ventilation	Ventilation system in operation from 4 a.m. to 6 p.m.
Exterior wall	42 cm thick brick walls
Interior wall	30 cm thick brick walls
Ceiling	Reinforced concrete ceiling with acoustic ceiling

Klassenzimmer Nordostfassade (Room A176)

Floor space	49,7 m²
Orientation of the windows	North-East
Window glazing	Thermal insulation glazing (built in 2018) (Total energy transmittance glazing 52 %)
Shading	Tree in front of the windows, only internal glare protection (no external sun protection)
Ventilation	Ventilation system in operation from 4 a.m. to 6 p.m.
Exterior wall	42 cm thick brick walls
Interior wall	30 cm thick brick walls
Ceiling	Reinforced concrete ceiling with acoustic ceiling

Ehrenfried-Walther-von-Tschirnhaus-Gymnasium in Dresden: Altbauteil

b Survey of students on heat stress

General Information

Pupils from two classrooms were surveyed on four different days about the perception of heat stress. In room 161 there were students of the 7th grade, in room 176 of the 8th grade. On the typical summer day (survey day 27.08.2024), 25 people in room 161 and 24 people in room 176 took part. On the hot day of the survey (14.08.2024), there were 28 students in each of the two rooms.

Source: Christoph Schünemann, 06/2024

Summer Day (27.08.2024)

Hot day (14.08.2024)

Room 161 um 11:30		Room 176 um 11:20	
Exterior	23.1 °C	Exterior	23.1 °C
Indoor	25.3 °C	Indoor	27.7 °C

The values in the pie chart show the number of responses in each class on the day of the survey.

Room 161 at 11:00		Room 176 at 10:00	
Exterior	29.9 °C	Exterior	29.3 °C
Indoor	27.2 °C	Indoor	27.8 °C

● Cold ● Cool ● OK ● Warm ● Hot ● No information

Pie charts to compare the temperatures perceived by the students in both classrooms: on a typical summer day (left) and on a hot day (right).

● Very well ● Well ● OK ● Unwell ● Very unwell ● no information

On a typical summer day (left), most students found room 161 okay, while room 176 was mostly unpleasant.

● Not tired ● Something tired ● Very tired ● No information

The reported feeling of fatigue was similar on both days, but slightly lower in room 161.

Circumstances during the survey

Room 161	Room 176
Ventilation through open window	Glare protection for interiors
Glare protection for interiors	Glare protection for interiors

Room 161	Room 176
Cross ventilation through open door and window	Ventilation through open room door
Glare protection for interiors	Glare protection for interiors

Conclusion

The perceived heat stress in room 176 was significantly higher than in room 161, both on a typical summer day and on a hot day, due to the south-east orientation (strong sunlight from early morning), small room size and lack of external shading. This is also reflected in the significantly worse well-being of the students in room 176. Another reason could also be the lack of window ventilation, because room 176, for example, was 27.7°C warm on August 27 at the time of the survey, although there was only 23.1°C outside.

Ehrenfried-Walther-von-Tschirnhaus-Gymnasium in Dresden: Altbauteil

c Temperature measurements and simulations in the classroom

Outdoor temperature measurement with KLIPS sensor

- Outside temperature
- School operations

The outside temperature was recorded with a KLIPS temperature sensor in the street space 300 m away (Leubnitzer Str., Dresden) in the summer of 2024. The outside temperature from 5.8 to 11.9.2024 is shown here. This study period was heavily heat-laden and showed 14 hot days (maximum outside temperature above 30°C), 4 tropical nights (minimum outside temperature at night above 20°C) and 14 tropical nights (maximum outside temperature at night above 20°C) and 14 tropical nights. 15 warm nights (minimum outside temperature at night above 18°C).

Classroom interior measurements

- School operations
- Temperature in room A161
- Temperature in room A176
- Outside temperature

In the period from 5.8 to 11.9.2024, both classrooms did not exceed the critical room temperature of 30°C, but almost permanently exceeded the comfort temperature of 26°C. The maximum temperature for room 176 is just under 30°C, that of room 161 almost 29°C.

Room 176 is significantly more heat-stressed than room 161 due to its south-east orientation, lack of sun protection and smaller size. This can also be seen in the rapid increase in room temperatures in the early morning hours.

Thermal building simulations of the current state (classroom 176)

3-dimensional model of the two classrooms in the thermal building simulation

The comparison of the simulated with the measured room temperature curve in the actual state is satisfactory using the local climate and assuming that a window is open in the period from 8 a.m. to 2 p.m. (weekdays), provided that the outside temperature is less than the room temperature and two more windows are opened every 10 minutes for fresh air supply (regardless of the room temperature) (including operation of the ventilation system).

Ehrenfried-Walther-von-Tschirnhaus-Gymnasium in Dresden: Altbauteil

d Effectiveness of heat adaptation measures and recommendations

Simulations of heat adaptation measures

Effectiveness of adaptation measures to reduce heat stress

The bar diagram shows the overtemperature degree hours (ÜTG) for different simulation variants of both classrooms. The ÜTG indicate how many hours and how much the comfort temperature of 26°C per year (Kh/a) is exceeded in the classroom. While v0 represents the reference (actual state) of the room, the other variants show the following differences:

- Strong increase in the ÜTG in room 176 without the shading of the tree in front of it (v2b)
- High effectiveness of external sun protection to reduce heat stress (v1)
- The operation of the ventilation system in continuous operation is also very effective in cooling the rooms through the cool outside air at night (v8).

Temperaturverläufe des Klassenraumes 176 für verschiedene Varianten

The above-mentioned findings are also clear in the illustration of the temperature curve for room 176 on the left. Without the shading of the tree, which some rooms on the south-east side of the school building have, the heat load is about 2°C higher with peak temperatures of over 32°C.

Recommendations

The measurements, surveys, simulations and comparison with the classrooms of other school buildings lead to the following assessment and recommendation regarding the reduction of heat stress:

Classrooms on the south-east side (street side) in particular are heat-stressed with room temperatures of up to 30 °C. This can be even more critical for some classrooms than for the examined room 176, if they are not partially shaded by trees in front of them, which reduces the room temperature by about 2°C. Even though the total energy transmittance of the glazing of the recently installed windows is low at 52% (it is not solar control glazing with a transmittance < 40%), it is so high that external sun protection would be very effective (temperature reduction > 1°C). A possible retrofit would have to be coordinated with the monument office. Furthermore, we recommend more intelligent operation of the ventilation system. This should go into operation at night as soon as the outside temperature is significantly lower than that of many classrooms. On hot days, the ventilation system should only be in operation during school hours so as not to transport additional warm outside air into the classrooms. A combination of these structural and technical measures can significantly reduce the heat load in the classrooms, together with adapted behaviour and school organisational measures. General recommendations, derived from the comparison of the school buildings examined, can be found here:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19651356>